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THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN LANGUAGE AND CULTURE

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Annotation. The article presents the concepts of language and culture as a means of communication and intercultural competence of an individual. Approaches to the study of the problem of continuous connection between language and culture are analysed by the author.

Keywords: culture, language, relationship between language and culture, communication

Human communication is one of the most significant topics on linguists', anthropologists', psychologists', and philosophers' thoughts today. Since it is the most important means of communication among human beings, the relation between language, culture, and their mutual interactions have high significance. The relevance of the problem "language and culture" was initially put forth by V. Humboldt, who claims that language expresses "the objective reality of the nation" and "cultural spirit" [1, 370-377]. He outlined the following basic concepts: 1) the material and spiritual cultures are embodied in language; 2) any culture has its national character presented in language; 3) language of one specific culture is an expression of "national spirit"; 4) the subject of "language and culture" is studied by an individual or community.

Another scholar Levi-Strauss determines the language as “the product of the culture and its constituents” [2, 26]. American anthropologist and linguist E.Sapir states that the language is tightly coupled with culture and that language is “germinated” from culture and further reflects it [3, 223]. Thus, according to the statements given, it follows that the language is the main means to store, transfer and reflect culture. This postulate has become a substantial one to new interdisciplinary sciences: linguistics and culturology in the last decades of the XX century.

Generally speaking, language is introduced by Crystal [4, 1992] as “the systematic, conventional use of sounds, signs or written symbols in a human society for communication and self-expression”. Similarly, Emmitt and Pollock [5, 1997] believe that language is a system of arbitrary signs which is accepted by a group and society of users. According to Chase [6, 1969], using language is a means of thinking, communicating with others, and forming one's perspective on the world.

Today, in every field, in humanities, every research requires a general view of culture. It is utilized in linguistics, history, psychology, sociology, and archaeology, among other fields. Even the idea that man is a cultured animal has been floated. That is to say, the factor which differentiates the human being's behavior from the behavior of animal is culture [7, 2005]. According to sociology, culture is generally defined as the sum of inherited and innate ideas, attitudes, beliefs, values, and knowledge that make up or form the shared premises of social behavior. Similar to this, culture is defined by anthropologists and ethnologists as the full range of practices and beliefs of a particular group of people who share similar traditions, which are conveyed, distributed, and highlighted by members of the group [8, 2003].

There are about two or three hundred and even more definitions of culture. With respect to the definition of culture, Edward Sapir (1956) says that culture is a system of behaviour and modes that depend on the unconsciousness. Rocher, an anthropologist, believes that “Culture is a connection of ideas and feelings

accepted by the majority of people in a society” [9, 142]. Undeniably, culture is learned and shared within social groups and is conveyed by non-genetic ways. According to Goodenough (1996), culture is an organized grouping of individuals who follow a particular way of life. Therefore, culture is the only distinction between human and animals, culture is for men, only. T. S. Eliot (1961) considers culture as a capital means for developing the process of a society, for helping economic stabilization and political security. Spencer (1986) believes that the super organic factor is only for man, whereas; the other two factors are the same for a man and animal.

The term "culture" should not be understood in its traditional sense but rather in what may be called its anthropological sense. In reality, Herder suggested this use of the term, but it wasn't until roughly eighty years later that anthropologists using the English language accepted it. In this second definition, culture is used without implying a straight line of human development from barbarism to civilization or placing any prior importance on the aesthetic or intellectual quality of a particular society's art, literature, institutions and so on. In this sense of the term, which has spread from anthropology to the other social sciences, every society has its own culture; and different subgroups within a society may have their own distinctive subculture. Herder's promotion of the word culture in this sense was bound up with this thesis of the interdependence of language and thought, on the one hand, and, on the other, with his view that a nation's language and culture were manifestations of its distinctive national spirit or mind. Indeed, many other writers in the Romantic movement had similar ideas. This is one strand in the complex historical development of the so-called Sapir-Whorf hypothesis, which dominated all discussion of language and culture.

Although the word culture is now widely employed in the social sciences, and especially by anthropologists, in the sense that has just been identified, it can be defined, technically, in several different ways. Culture may be described as socially acquired knowledge, to be precise, as the knowledge that someone has by virtue of his being a member of a particular society. Two points must be made here

about the use of the word knowledge. First, it is to be understood as covering practical knowledge: both knowing how to do something and knowing that something is or is not so. Second, in terms of propositional knowledge, it is the belief that something is true rather than its actual truth or falsity that matters. Additionally, we must recognize that multiple sorts or levels of truth exist across the majority, if not all, civilizations. For instance, the reality of a religious or mythological statement is evaluated differently from that of a straightforward factual report. When viewed from this angle, science itself is a component of culture. And in the discussion of the relationship between language and culture no priority should be given to scientific knowledge over common-sense knowledge or even superstition.

Brown convinced there is a connection between language and culture. He says, "It is apparent that culture... becomes highly important in the learning of a second language. The two are tightly entwined; a language is a component of a culture, and a culture is a part of a language. (Brown, 2000, p. 177).

We mostly conduct our social lives through language. It is linked to culture in a variety of intricate ways when it is employed in communication contexts. The most widespread and possibly the most intricate and fascinating of all human abilities is language.

Indeed, there are various ways in which people use the spoken, written, the speaker's tone of voice, accent, conversational style, gestures and facial expression. Language represents cultural reality in all of its verbal and nonverbal facets. That is, culture has a direct effect on language. Language and culture are closely correlated.

Speakers perceive their language as a representation of their social identity and use it to identify both themselves and other people. The speakers of this language frequently interpret the ban on its usage as a rejection of their social circle and culture. So, we can say that language symbolizes cultural reality.

Concerning the above discussion we can say that language is an inevitable part of culture because: 1) it is a part of culture that we inherit from our ancestors;

2) language is the dominant tool with the help of which we learn culture; 3) language is a significant phenomenon – to understand the essence of culture (religion, literature, science) one should consider these phenomena as codes generated within language.

In conclusion, we can stress that languages reflect culture. It is often said that language is a “mirror” of a particular community because language reflects its spiritual and material cultures. Thus, it can be claimed that there are close relations between language and culture.

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